

Report

Conceptual design of an application-specific data quality matrix for agrosystem data

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Acronyms

AS-DQM Application-Specific Data Quality Matrix. [D](#), [3](#), [5–13](#)

DFFP Data-Fitness-For-Purpose. [3–5](#), [7](#), [9](#), [13](#)

JSON JavaScript Object Notation. [D](#), [3](#), [8](#), [10](#), [13](#)

LLM Large Language Models. [3](#), [6–8](#), [12](#), [13](#)

1. Introduction

High-quality, well-documented data are a fundamental prerequisite for data reuse in agricultural and environmental research (Ewert et al., 2023; Specka et al., 2023). Within FAIRagro, data quality is understood not only as an intrinsic, universally valid property of a dataset, but also as a characteristic that depends on the requirements of a specific scientific or operational application. A dataset that is suitable for regional-scale modelling, for example, may be unsuitable for field-level decision support or operational management.

Agrosystem data are particularly heterogeneous with respect to spatial scale, temporal resolution, measurement practices, and uncertainty characteristics. Typical FAIRagro use cases involve combinations of different spatial data sets like long-term agricultural field experiments, phenological observations, geodata products, remote sensing, and model outputs (Lokers et al., 2016). For such data, key quality aspects include, among others, spatial and temporal representativity, aggregation effects, methodological transparency, uncertainty quantification, and documented limitations. While many of these aspects are discussed in scientific publications and dataset documentation, they are rarely formalized in a way that allows systematic comparison, automated discovery, or machine-assisted assessment of fitness-for-use.

FAIRagro Measure 3.3 addresses this gap by developing application-oriented approaches for assessing and documenting geodata quality and [Data-Fitness-For-Purpose \(DFFP\)](#) (Ewert et al., 2023). In contrast to generic quality checklists or purely metric-driven approaches, Measure 3.3 emphasizes the relationship between data characteristics, uncertainty, and the expected quality of analysis outcomes for specific applications. This perspective complements related FAIRagro activities, including the definition of quality metadata descriptors (Measure 3.1), plausibility checks for long-term experiments (Measure 1.4), and quality aspects in agrosystem robotics and sensor data (Measure 3.4).

This deliverable (D3.3.1) presents the conceptual design of an [Application-Specific Data Quality Matrix \(AS-DQM\)](#), developed within FAIRagro Measure 3.3. The [AS-DQM](#) provides a structured, machine-actionable framework for capturing and representing application-specific data quality information and [DFFP](#) based exclusively on existing textual sources. These sources include scientific publications, dataset documentation, workflow descriptions, and repository metadata. No quality metrics are computed from raw data; instead, the approach formalizes what dataset creators and users already report about data quality, uncertainty, validation, and limitations.

To operationalize this concept, the [AS-DQM](#) combines structure-preserving document preprocessing with [Large Language Models \(LLM\)](#)-assisted information extraction and schema-based normalization. The resulting quality descriptions are expressed in a standardized [JavaScript Object Notation \(JSON\)](#) format, enabling automated querying, comparison, and integration into FAIRagro services such as quality-aware search, dataset recommendation, and FAIRness monitoring.

The report is structured as follows. Section 2 introduces the conceptual background and the application-dependent notion of data quality and fitness-for-purpose underlying the [AS-DQM](#). Section 3 describes the methodology, including document preprocessing, [LLM](#)-assisted extraction, schema definition, and validation. Section 4 presents a pilot application of the approach using a phenology-related dataset and associated scientific literature. Section 5 discusses strengths, limitations, and implications for FAIRagro. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the main findings and outlines directions for future work.

2. Conceptual Background: Data Quality and Fitness-for-Use

2.1. From Generic Data Quality to Application-Dependent Assessment

Data quality is commonly described using generic dimensions such as accuracy, completeness, consistency, timeliness, and provenance (e.g., ISO19157-1, 2023). These dimensions are widely used in data management standards and quality assessment frameworks and provide a useful starting point for evaluating datasets in a general sense. However, in agricultural and environmental research, such generic notions are often insufficient to determine whether a dataset is suitable for a specific scientific or operational application.

In agrosystem research, the suitability of data depends strongly on the intended use. For example, spatially interpolated phenological data may be sufficiently accurate for regional-scale trend analysis or model calibration, while being unsuitable for field-level operational decision-making. Similarly, long-term experimental data may be adequate for studying relative treatment effects but require additional plausibility checks before being used for absolute yield comparisons or cross-site synthesis.

This observation motivates a shift from viewing data quality as an intrinsic property of a dataset towards an *application-dependent* perspective. In this perspective, data quality is evaluated relative to the requirements, assumptions, and tolerances of a specific application rather than against a universal set of thresholds.

2.2. Fitness-for-Purpose as a Core Concept

Assessment of the suitability of data can be achieved by a Data-Fitness-For-Use (DFFU) or DFFP evaluation (Pôças et al., 2014). DFFU criteria describes the general suitability of a data set for further use and thus refer to the intrinsic quality of the data such as completeness, accuracy, consistency, and timeliness ready to be used according to non-functional requirements (Lacagnina et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2013). DFFP criteria are more context-dependent and emphasize data suitability for a specific application or purpose according to the user's functional requirements (Lacagnina et al., 2022). Lokers et al., 2016 pointed out that thematic "accuracy of data and data sources is [also] highly associated with trust and with having confidence that the quality of data is sufficient to serve as evidence base for critical decision making". This statement is supported by the results of the survey, according to which "the reputation of data providers was identified as a key factor in data set selection" (Yang et al., 2013).

There are DFFP approaches that aim to enable users to select the appropriate [*here: spatial*] data for their specific needs. However, these approaches differ significantly in their perspectives, methodologies, and outputs. They range from practical toolkits and quantitative frameworks to standardised rating systems (e.g., Fischer et al., 2023; Höck et al., 2020; Petutschnig et al., 2024; Wentz & Shimizu, 2018). All of these approaches acknowledge that DFFP is not an intrinsic property of data, but rather is defined by the context and requirements of a specific end user or application. The approaches thus aim at a retrospective evaluation of data from the user's perspective.

Furthermore, DFFP does not imply that a dataset is "good" or "bad" in absolute terms. Instead, it reflects whether known constraints are acceptable for a particular purpose. Importantly, these constraints are often already described in scientific publications and dataset documentation, but typically in narrative form, making systematic comparison and querying difficult.

Within FAIRagro, the DFFP concept is particularly relevant because many reuse scenarios involve combining heterogeneous datasets across disciplines, scales, and time periods. In such settings, transparent documentation of assumptions, validation procedures, and uncertainty becomes as important as traditional metadata describing content and format.

Figure 1: **Application-Specific Data Quality Matrix (AS-DQM)** as extension of data quality and meta data description.

2.3. Positioning within FAIRagro Measure 3.3

FAIRagro Measure 3.3 explicitly addresses the need for application-oriented approaches to data quality and fitness-for-use (Ewert et al., 2023). The measure focuses on identifying relevant quality aspects for typical spatial agrosystem applications, formalizing these aspects in a structured way, and enabling their use in application-specific queries and search interfaces.

Measure 3.3 complements other FAIRagro activities that address data quality from different perspectives. Measure 3.1 focuses on extending FAIRagro metadata schemas with quality-related descriptors, Measure 1.4 addresses plausibility and consistency issues in long-term agricultural field experiments, and Measure 3.4 investigates quality aspects in high-frequency sensor and robotics data. Together, these measures contribute to a comprehensive quality framework that spans data production, documentation, assessment, and reuse.

The contribution of Measure 3.3 lies in bridging the gap between generic quality descriptors and concrete application needs. Rather than defining additional fixed quality metrics, Measure 3.3 aims to make explicit how documented data characteristics and uncertainties constrain or enable specific types of analyses.

2.4. Implications for the AS-DQM Approach

The **AS-DQM** developed in this deliverable operationalizes the **DFFP** concept by systematically extracting quality-relevant information from textual sources associated with a dataset. These sources include scientific publications, technical documentation, workflow descriptions, and repository metadata. By structuring this information in a machine-actionable form, the **AS-DQM** enables datasets to be evaluated and compared with respect to specific application contexts. Importantly, the framework does not compute new quality metrics from raw data. Instead, it formalizes existing knowledge about data quality, uncertainty, validation, strengths, and limitations as reported by data providers and users. Against this background, an **AS-DQM** can be considered as an element extending data quality and meta data description (Figure 1). This document-driven, application-oriented perspective provides the conceptual foundation for the methodology presented in the following sections.

3. Methodology: The AS-DQM Framework

This section describes the methodology used to design and implement the **AS-DQM**. The methodology follows a document-driven, application-oriented approach to data quality assessment, in which

quality-relevant information is systematically extracted from textual sources associated with a dataset and formalized in a machine-actionable representation. The overall workflow comprises document preprocessing, semantic information extraction, schema-based normalization, and structured output generation.

3.1. Overview of the AS-DQM Workflow

The **AS-DQM** workflow is designed to transform heterogeneous, largely narrative descriptions of datasets into a structured representation that supports application-specific data quality and fitness-for-use assessment. Rather than computing new quality metrics from raw data, the approach operationalizes the fitness-for-use concept by formalizing what is already documented by data providers and users.

At a high level, the workflow consists of four main stages:

1. ingestion and preprocessing of dataset-related documents,
2. extraction of quality-relevant concepts using **LLMs**,
3. normalization and validation against a predefined schema,
4. serialization into machine-actionable output formats.

These stages are illustrated in the pipeline diagram shown in Figure 2. The figure provides a visual overview of the workflow, showing how input documents are converted from PDF to enriched Markdown, processed with LLM-assisted extraction, normalized according to the schema, and finally transformed into the application-specific data quality matrix.

Figure 2: Pipeline architecture of the AS-DQM framework. The workflow illustrates the transformation of dataset-related documents from PDF to structured, machine-actionable representations, highlighting where the application-specific matrix is generated.

Each stage is then described in detail in the following subsections, explicitly linking the workflow steps to the conceptual notion of application-dependent data quality introduced in Section 2.

3.2. Document Sources and Ingestion

The evidence base for the **AS-DQM** consists exclusively of textual materials that accompany a dataset throughout its lifecycle. These materials typically include:

- scientific publications describing data generation or use,
- technical documentation and data descriptors,
- workflow and processing descriptions,
- repository metadata and README files.

These documents contain essential information about methodological assumptions, validation strategies, uncertainty characteristics, and intended applications. However, this information is usu-

ally distributed across multiple sources and expressed in narrative form, which limits its reuse in automated discovery and assessment workflows.

By treating these documents as the primary input, the [AS-DQM](#) ensures that quality assessment remains grounded in documented evidence and does not introduce additional requirements for data providers.

3.3. Structure-Preserving Document Preprocessing

Scientific publications and technical reports are commonly distributed as PDF files, which pose challenges for automated information extraction due to complex layouts, multi-column text, tables, figures, and embedded equations. Simple PDF-to-text conversion often destroys structural information that is essential for correctly interpreting content related to data quality and validation.

To address this challenge, the [AS-DQM](#) workflow employs the `docling` library for structure-preserving document conversion (Auer et al., 2024; Docling Project, 2024). Docling performs layout analysis, optical character recognition where needed, and explicit extraction of headings, paragraphs, tables, figures, and captions. The output is an enriched Markdown representation that preserves the logical structure and semantic relationships of the original document. This preprocessing step is crucial for [DFFP](#) assessment because key quality information—such as validation results, uncertainty descriptions, or methodological constraints—is frequently presented in tables or figures rather than in plain text.

3.4. Multimodal Enrichment of Document Content

In addition to textual content, figures and visualizations in scientific documents often convey essential information about data quality, such as spatial coverage, sampling density, model performance, or uncertainty patterns. To make this information accessible for downstream extraction, the workflow optionally enriches documents with textual descriptions of images.

During preprocessing, figures are extracted and annotated using a multimodal [LLM](#). The resulting descriptions are embedded directly into the Markdown document as figure annotations. This multimodal enrichment allows subsequent extraction steps to consider both textual and visual evidence when identifying quality-relevant concepts.

By integrating image-based information, the [AS-DQM](#) reduces the risk that important quality constraints remain unrecognized simply because they are communicated visually rather than verbally.

3.5. LLM-Assisted Extraction of Quality-Relevant Concepts

Following preprocessing, the enriched document is processed by a [LLM](#) to identify and extract quality-relevant concepts. The extraction is guided by explicit instructions that reflect the application-dependent definition of data quality and fitness-for-use introduced in Section 2.

The [LLM](#) is tasked with identifying, among others, the following types of information:

- intended use cases and application contexts,
- spatial and temporal characteristics,
- methodological assumptions and processing steps,
- validation strategies and performance indicators,
- uncertainty characterization and limitations,
- recommended and discouraged usage scenarios.

The [LLM](#) does not infer or compute new metrics but extracts and structures information explicitly stated or implicitly described in the source documents. This ensures that the resulting quality description remains traceable to documented evidence and avoids over-interpretation.

3.6. Schema Definition and Normalization

To ensure consistency, comparability, and machine-actionability, all extracted information is normalized against a predefined schema that represents the conceptual structure of the [AS-DQM](#). The schema is implemented using Pydantic data models (Pydantic Project, 2023) and defines mandatory and optional fields for application context, quality indicators, uncertainty, validation, and fitness-for-use elements.

Schema-based normalization serves several purposes:

- it enforces consistent terminology and structure across datasets,
- it reduces ambiguity in [LLM](#) outputs,
- it enables validation and error detection,
- it supports downstream querying and integration.

This step directly supports FAIRagro Measure 3.3 by transforming narrative quality descriptions into structured elements that can be used in application-specific queries and search interfaces.

3.7. Validation and Provenance Tracking

All extracted [AS-DQM](#) records are validated against the schema to ensure structural correctness and internal consistency. Invalid or incomplete outputs are rejected or flagged for manual inspection. In addition, provenance information is recorded to maintain traceability between extracted quality statements and their source documents. This includes references to document sections, figures, or tables where relevant information was identified. Provenance tracking is essential for transparency and for building trust in semi-automated quality assessment workflows.

3.8. Output Formats and FAIRagro Integration

Validated [AS-DQM](#) records are serialized into a canonical [JSON](#) representation. This machine-actionable format enables automated processing and integration with FAIRagro services. In addition to [JSON](#), the framework supports alternative representations such as tabular exports and human-readable visualizations to facilitate inspection and comparison by data stewards and domain scientists. The resulting outputs are designed to support key FAIRagro use cases, including quality-aware dataset discovery, application-specific querying, fitness-for-use assessment, and continuous FAIRness monitoring.

4. Results: Pilot Application of the AS-DQM

This section presents the results of applying the [AS-DQM](#) framework to real-world agrosystem data. The objective of the pilot application is to demonstrate how the proposed methodology transforms narrative, heterogeneous documentation into a structured, machine-actionable representation of application-specific data quality and fitness-for-use ([Figure 3](#)).

The PHASE data set represents a Germany-wide and spatio-temporally consistent 1 km analysis-ready time series of interpolated days of the year. The data set covers the start dates of the phenological development stages of nine main crop types for the period between 1993 and 2022. The derivation of the 1972 records is based on phenological observations provided by Germany's national meteorological service and the PHASE model, which combines the concept of growing degree days with a geostatistical interpolation procedure (Gerstmann et al., 2016).

A main application of the resulting spatial dataset is the extraction of phenological windows or phases, which represent periods between two consecutive beginning stages of development (Möller et al., 2017), for any (available) year and the user-defined region (Möller et al., 2020). This information

Figure 3: Application-Specific Data Quality Matrix (AS-DQM) use case: The PHASE data set.

is relevant for applications such as the derivation of agricultural weather index derivation (Möller et al., 2019), weather insurance of crop production (Bucheli et al., 2023; Bucheli et al., 2020; Vroege et al., 2021), the analysis of extreme weather impacts on crop yields in Germany (Riedesel, Ma, et al., 2024; Riedesel et al., 2023; Riedesel, Möller, Piepho, et al., 2024) crop-type classification (Gerstmann et al., 2018) or soil erosion (Batista et al., 2025; Möller et al., 2017).

Two complementary pilot perspectives are presented. First, the approach is applied at the *dataset level* using the phenology data product as an example. Second, the approach is illustrated at the *application level* by extracting DFFP information from a scientific study that uses the phenology dataset for a concrete analytical purpose. Together, these perspectives reflect typical FAIRagro reuse scenarios (Riedesel et al., 2023).

4.1. Pilot Dataset: Germany-wide Phenology Time Series

The primary pilot dataset is the *Germany-wide time series of interpolated phenological observations* covering the period from 1993 to 2022. The dataset provides gridded Day-Of-Year estimates for the onset of phenological phases of major crop types at a spatial resolution of 1 km.

The dataset is representative of FAIRagro target use cases because it combines heterogeneous input data (volunteered phenological observations, meteorological data, and interpolation models), long temporal coverage, and explicitly documented uncertainty and validation procedures. The accompanying scientific publications and technical documentation provide a rich textual basis for document-driven quality extraction.

4.2. Document Corpus and Evidence Base

For the pilot application, the AS-DQM was applied to a corpus consisting of:

- peer-reviewed publications describing dataset generation and validation,
- dataset descriptors and repository metadata,
- methodological documentation of the processing workflow,
- applied studies using the phenology dataset, e.g., Riedesel et al., 2023, which evaluates the impact of heat and drought on winter wheat yields across Germany.

These documents collectively describe spatial and temporal coverage, interpolation methods, validation strategies, uncertainty estimates, and intended application domains. No raw data were accessed or processed as part of the pilot. Applying the [AS-DQM](#) to an application study illustrates how dataset-level quality metrics interact with real-world use cases, including spatial aggregation, phenology-based windowing, and uncertainty propagation. Short excerpts of the structured [AS-DQM JSON](#) outputs for the three application-level pilots—including soil erosion nowcasting (Batista et al., 2025), wheat yield under heat and drought stress (Riedesel et al., 2023), and standardized weather-index calculation (Möller et al., 2019)—are provided in Appendix B, with the full machine-readable [JSON](#) files publicly available on Zenodo (Hedayat Mahmoudi & Möller, 2025).

4.3. Extracted Quality and Fitness-for-Use Dimensions

Applying the [AS-DQM](#) extraction workflow resulted in a structured representation of quality-relevant information spanning multiple dimensions. Key extracted elements include:

- **Application context:** documented use cases such as regional phenology analysis, crop modelling, and index-based insurance.
- **Spatial and temporal characteristics:** national coverage, 1 km grid resolution, annual Day-Of-Year time series.
- **Validation framework:** external validation using training–test splits and distributional tests.
- **Performance indicators:** reported MAE, RMSE, coefficient of determination, and correlation metrics.
- **Uncertainty characterization:** global performance metrics and spatially explicit local uncertainty estimates derived from interpolation.
- **Strengths and limitations:** documented advantages, known constraints, and phase-dependent reliability.
- **Recommended and discouraged usage:** suitability for regional analyses and limitations for field-scale operational decision-making.

These elements directly reflect the application-dependent notion of data quality described in Section 2 and enable an explicit assessment of fitness-for-use rather than a generic quality score.

4.4. AS-DQM JSON Representation

All extracted information was normalized and serialized into the canonical [AS-DQM JSON](#) format. The resulting structure provides a comprehensive, machine-actionable quality profile of the phenology dataset, including application contexts, validation evidence, uncertainty descriptions, and explicit usage guidance.

Short excerpts of the structured [AS-DQM JSON](#) outputs for the application-level pilots are provided in Appendix B, while the complete machine-readable [JSON](#) files are publicly available on Zenodo (Hedayat Mahmoudi & Möller, 2025). The [JSON](#) structure enables automated comparison with other datasets, supports application-specific queries, and can be directly integrated into FAIRagro search and inventory services.

4.5. Illustrating Fitness-for-Use Reasoning

Beyond listing quality indicators, the [AS-DQM](#) explicitly captures the reasoning that links data characteristics to application suitability. For example, the dataset is identified as suitable for regional-to-national analyses where temporal accuracy requirements are on the order of several days, while it is documented as unsuitable for sub-kilometer, operational scheduling tasks.

This explicit representation of suitability and limitation statements illustrates how narrative quality information can be transformed into structured knowledge that supports informed reuse decisions.

4.6. Application-Level Pilot: Fitness-for-Use in a Scientific Study

To further demonstrate the application-oriented nature of the [AS-DQM](#), the framework was additionally applied to a peer-reviewed study that uses the phenology dataset for a specific analytical purpose. As an example, we consider a study investigating climate-phenology relationships using gridded phenological indicators (Riedesel et al., 2023).

Unlike dataset descriptors, application-focused publications often state implicit quality requirements, such as acceptable temporal uncertainty, minimum spatial representativity, or assumptions about data completeness. Applying the [AS-DQM](#) to such a study allows these implicit constraints to be extracted and formalized.

The extraction identified, among others:

- application-specific accuracy requirements for phenological timing,
- assumptions about spatial aggregation and representativity,
- tolerance to uncertainty in early versus late phenological phases,
- dependencies between phenology data quality and downstream model results.

Comparing the application-level [AS-DQM](#) profile with the dataset-level profile demonstrates how fitness-for-use emerges from the interaction between data characteristics and application requirements. This comparison highlights cases where a dataset may be generally well-documented but only conditionally suitable for a given analysis. This application-level perspective directly supports the objectives of FAIRagro Measure 3.3 by enabling quality-aware dataset selection and application-specific querying.

5. Discussion

This section discusses the results of the pilot application of the [AS-DQM](#) with respect to the conceptual goals of FAIRagro Measure 3.3. The discussion focuses on the strengths of the document-driven, application-oriented approach, its current limitations, and its implications for FAIRagro infrastructure and future development.

5.1. Added Value of an Application-Oriented Quality Perspective

The pilot application demonstrates that substantial information relevant to data quality and fitness-for-use is already available in textual sources accompanying agrosystem datasets. Scientific publications, dataset documentation, and workflow descriptions frequently contain detailed statements on validation strategies, uncertainty characteristics, and suitable application contexts. However, this information is typically scattered across documents and expressed in narrative form, which limits its accessibility for automated discovery and reuse.

By formalizing this information in a structured and machine-actionable representation, the [AS-DQM](#) makes explicit the relationship between documented data characteristics and application-specific requirements. This represents a key contribution of Measure 3.3, as it shifts the focus from

generic, one-size-fits-all quality indicators towards explicit fitness-for-use reasoning. In particular, the ability to capture documented limitations and non-suitable usage scenarios is essential for responsible data reuse but is rarely supported by existing metadata standards.

5.2. Complementarity to Metric-Based Quality Assessment

The [AS-DQM](#) does not aim to replace metric-based data quality assessment approaches. Quantitative quality metrics derived directly from data remain essential for many use cases, especially in data production and quality control phases. Instead, the [AS-DQM](#) complements these approaches by addressing a different layer of the quality landscape.

While metrics provide numerical summaries of specific aspects such as accuracy or completeness, they often lack contextual information about how these metrics were obtained, under which assumptions they are valid, and for which applications they are meaningful. The document-driven approach explicitly captures this contextual information and preserves links to the original evidence. In this sense, the [AS-DQM](#) acts as an interpretative layer that supports informed use of both datasets and associated quality metrics.

5.3. Limitations of Document-Driven and LLM-Assisted Extraction

Despite its strengths, the proposed approach has several limitations that need to be acknowledged:

1. The quality and completeness of the resulting [AS-DQM](#) records depend directly on the quality of the underlying documentation. Datasets with sparse or poorly structured documentation will yield correspondingly limited quality profiles.
2. The use of [LLMs](#) introduces uncertainty related to semantic interpretation and information extraction. Although schema-based normalization and validation reduce the risk of inconsistent outputs, the approach cannot fully eliminate ambiguity or misinterpretation, particularly for implicit assumptions or nuanced methodological statements. For this reason, provenance tracking and the option for human inspection remain essential components of the workflow.
3. The current pilot focuses on extracting quality-relevant information from static documents. Dynamic aspects of data quality, such as temporal changes in data production workflows or evolving uncertainty characteristics, are not yet addressed and represent an important area for future work.

5.4. Implications for FAIRagro Infrastructure

From an infrastructure perspective, the [AS-DQM](#) provides a foundation for integrating application-oriented quality information into FAIRagro services. The structured output can be used to support quality-aware dataset discovery, application-specific filtering, and dataset recommendation within FAIRagro portals.

In combination with quality metadata descriptors developed in Measure 3.1 and plausibility checks addressed in Measure 1.4, the [AS-DQM](#) contributes to a layered quality framework that spans data production, documentation, assessment, and reuse. The approach is particularly well suited for legacy datasets and complex data products for which recomputation of quality metrics is impractical or impossible.

5.5. Outlook and Future Development

Future work within Measure 3.3 will focus on extending the conceptual coverage of the [AS-DQM](#) schema, refining extraction strategies, and evaluating the approach across a broader range of agrosystem data types. Potential extensions include tighter integration with FAIRagro search interfaces, support for interactive [DFFP](#) queries, and improved human-in-the-loop workflows for validation and curation. In the longer term, application-oriented quality representations such as the [AS-DQM](#) can support more transparent and responsible data reuse by making assumptions, uncertainties, and limitations explicit and machine-readable.

6. Summary and Conclusions

This deliverable (D3.3.1) presents the conceptual design and pilot implementation of the [AS-DQM](#), developed within FAIRagro Measure 3.3. The objective of the [AS-DQM](#) is to support application-oriented data quality assessment by making documented information on data characteristics, uncertainty, validation, and limitations explicitly available in a structured and machine-actionable form.

Building on the notion that data quality is inherently application-dependent, the [AS-DQM](#) shifts the focus from generic quality indicators to [DFFP](#) reasoning. Rather than computing new quality metrics from raw data, the approach formalizes existing knowledge contained in scientific publications, dataset documentation, and workflow descriptions. This document-driven strategy enables transparent and evidence-based quality assessment while avoiding additional burdens for data providers.

The methodology combines structure-preserving document preprocessing, multimodal enrichment, [LLM](#)-assisted information extraction, and schema-based normalization. The resulting quality profiles are expressed in a standardized [JSON](#) format that supports automated querying, comparison, and integration into FAIRagro services.

A pilot application using a Germany-wide phenology dataset demonstrates the feasibility and added value of the approach. The results show that essential [DFFP](#) information—such as suitable application contexts, documented uncertainties, validation strategies, and explicit usage limitations—can be systematically extracted and represented in a form suitable for quality-aware dataset discovery and reuse.

In combination with related FAIRagro activities, the [AS-DQM](#) contributes to a layered quality framework that spans data documentation, assessment, and reuse. Within Measure 3.3, it provides a foundation for future developments such as application-specific search interfaces, dataset recommendation, and interactive fitness-for-use assessment.

Overall, this work demonstrates that application-oriented, document-driven data quality representations are a viable and valuable complement to metric-based approaches, particularly for complex and heterogeneous agrosystem data.

Appendix

A. Docling-Based Markdown Output Showcase

This section shows the enriched Markdown output generated by the Docling pipeline for the paper “A framework for standardized calculation of weather indices in Germany”. The output is LLM-ready and preserves document structure, tables, figures, and automatically generated image descriptions.

Markdown Text Excerpt

```
## A framework for standardized calculation of weather indices in Germany

Markus Mller  Juliane Doms  Henning Gerstmann  Til Feike

## Abstract

Climate change has been recognized as a main driver in the increasing occurrence of extreme weather. Weather indices (WIs) are used to assess extreme weather conditions regarding their impact on crop yields. Designing WIs is challenging, since complex and dynamic cropclimate relationships have to be considered.

In this study, we introduce a WI design framework for Germany based on public and open raster data with long-term spatio-temporal availability. The operational process chain enables the dynamic and automatic definition of phenological phases for the main cultivated crops in Germany. Within these temporal bounds, WIs can be calculated for any year and test site in a reproducible and transparent manner.

## Introduction

- Weather indices can be objectively measured during crop growth, but relevant weather impacts often occur only during specific phenological phases.
- Fixed calendar-based reference periods may cause temporal inaccuracies.
- Phenology-based temporal windows offer a dynamic alternative that reflects inter-annual variability.
- Raster-based geodata reduce spatial inaccuracies caused by station distance and data gaps.
```

Table Example from Markdown

Table 1. Distances [km] between test sites and weather stations (D_{WS}) or phenological observations (D_{PS}) as well as Spearman correlation coefficients (ρ) between test site-specific weather indices based on station (WI_S) or raster data (WI_R).

TS	D_WS	D_PS	(WI_S, WI_R)
1	11	11	0.85
2	5	11	0.86
3	10	18	0.87
4	12	27	0.90
5	8	32	0.22
6	2	15	0.39
7	13	90	0.90
8	13	30	0.45
9	5	18	0.51

10	21	29	0.28
11	21	0	0.37
12	21	14	0.34
13	26	5	0.36
14	23	0	0.71
15	8	11	0.83
16	8	20	0.87

Annotated Figure Example

Figure 4: Fig. 2. Principle workflow for the derivation of a phase-specific and raster-based weather index (WIR^R). RU – reference unit – DOY – phenological day of the year – PDOY – daily precipitation – $DOY^{A,B}$ – DOYs of a phase’s start and end – DEM – digital elevation model – E – elevation – Y – year – PHASE – model for the interpolation of beginning phenological phases – read_regnie – model for the import of REGNIE data.

LLM-Generated Figure Description: The image is a three-part flow diagram illustrating the process of generating a phase-specific raster-based weather index. On the left, the input data consist of phenological observations defined by day of year (DOY) at point locations, a digital elevation model (DEM) providing elevation (E) values on a 1×1 km raster, and daily precipitation data (REGNIE) represented as precipitation rasters (PDOY) at the same spatial resolution. Phenological observations and DEM data are processed by the PHASE model, which integrates growing degree day concepts with spatial interpolation to generate phenological windows defined by rasterized start and end days of year (DOY^A and DOY^B). In parallel, precipitation data are imported via a processing step labeled *read_regnie*. Both data streams are combined at the reference-unit (RU) level to produce the final output shown on the right: a three-dimensional surface representing the raster-based weather index (WIR^R) as a function of precipitation and day of year, with the phase boundaries DOY^A and DOY^B indicated on the surface.

B. Exemplary AS-DQM JSON Outputs for Application-Level Pilots

This appendix provides **short excerpts** of the **AS-DQM JSON** representations generated for the three exemplary application-level pilots. The **full machine-readable JSON files** are publicly available on Zenodo (Hedayat Mahmoudi & Möller, 2025). The pilots include

- Soil erosion nowcasting using machine learning (Batista et al., 2025),
- Wheat yield under heat and drought stress in Germany (Riedesel et al., 2023),
- Standardized calculation of weather indices in Germany (Möller et al., 2019).

B.1. Soil Erosion AS-DQM JSON Excerpt

```

1  [
2  {
3    {
4      "application_area": [
5        "Parcel-level nowcasting of soil-erosion occurrence and relative severity",
6        "Regional-scale dynamic monitoring of arable land erosion (demonstrated for Bavaria)"
7      ],
8      "intended_use": "Provide near-real-time predictions to support farmers, advisors, and regional land
9        managers in monitoring erosion events and planning soil conservation actions.",
10     "spatial_scale": "Parcel-level outputs aggregated from 530 m resolution covariates; regional
11       summaries for Bavaria, Germany",
12     "temporal_scale": "Event-based nowcasts with daily updates; trained on spring/summer 20112012 heavy
13       rainfall events",
14     "validation_metrics": [
15       "Occurrence detection: overall accuracy 88% (recall 89%, precision 84%)",
16       "Severity ranking (classes 03): overall accuracy 50%; class 3 recall 63%, precision 55%"
17     ],
18     "strengths": [
19       "Machine learning-based random forest ensemble for probabilistic prediction",
20       "Integration of aerial imagery, radar rainfall, NDVI, phenology, and topographic/soil data",
21       "Parcel-level uncertainty estimates and applicability-domain flags"
22     ],
23     "limitations": [
24       "Dependent on training data coverage; limited to represented crops, regions, and seasons",
25       "Outputs are relative severity rankings, not absolute soil-loss estimates",
26       "Interrill erosion not detectable if not visible in aerial imagery"
27     ],
28     "reproducibility_and_fairness": [
29       "Training labels and code available on Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/records/11072309)",
30       "Data-cube APIs and standardized formats ensure interoperability and reusability"
31     ]
32   }
33 ]

```

B.2. Wheat Yield AS-DQM JSON Excerpt

```
1 [
2   {
3     "application_area": [
4       "Crop yield impact assessment under heat and drought stress",
5       "Climate risk analysis for agriculture",
6       "Regional yield vulnerability mapping at municipality level"
7     ],
8     "intended_use": "Quantify timing- and intensity-specific wheat yield losses across German
9       Soil-Climate Regions to support research, policy, insurance design, and adaptation planning.",
10    "spatial_scale": "Municipality-level aggregation from 11 km weather and phenology grids; SCR
11      stratification for region-specific coefficients",
12    "temporal_scale": "Annual yield observations (19952019) with daily weather and PAW grids",
13    "validation_metrics": [
14      "Variance reduction (VR) per weather index",
15      "SCR-specific coefficient significance (p-values)",
16      "Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) for model selection"
17    ],
18    "strengths": [
19      "Phenology-aware indices (PHASE model) capturing sensitive crop periods",
20      "Mixed-effects regression with fixed and random effects accounting for spatial/temporal variation",
21      "Large farm panel (~11,500 farms) and gridded weather data allow spatially-explicit yield-loss
22      mapping"
23    ],
24    "limitations": [
25      "Explanatory power of individual weather indices is limited (max VR ~ -2.1%)",
26      "Results dependent on interpolated weather, phenology, and soil data",
27      "Field-scale precision or non-German regions require recalibration",
28      "Sparse extreme events reduce coefficient stability"
29    ],
30    "reproducibility_and_fairness": [
31      "Minimal dataset published on Zenodo (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8076295)",
32      "Workflow fully documented in Methods and Supporting Files; uses standard spatial and phenology
33      products for interoperability",
34      "FADN yield data restricted; full reuse requires BMEL permission"
35    ]
36  }
37 ]
```

B.3. Weather-indices AS-DQM JSON Excerpt

```
1  [
2  {
3    "application_area": [
4      "Agricultural risk management",
5      "Weather-index based insurance (WII)",
6      "Crop yield modeling",
7      "Agro-climatic monitoring"
8    ],
9    "intended_use": "Standardized calculation of spatially-explicit, phenology-aware weather indices for
10   Germany to reduce spatial and temporal basis risk and provide quantified uncertainty for decision
11   support.",
12   "spatial_scale": "11 km raster grids aggregated to reference units or regional zones;
13   phenology-aware pixel-level precision",
14   "temporal_scale": "Daily precipitation and temperature rasters (19942014) with phenology-dependent
15   windows",
16   "validation_metrics": [
17     "RMSE and R comparing raster-based vs station-based WIs",
18     "Spearman rank correlation () per site and pixel",
19     "Variable importance for regression and Random Forest models"
20   ],
21   "strengths": [
22     "Phenology-aware dynamic windows improve temporal accuracy of WIs",
23     "Regression-kriging interpolation reduces spatial basis risk",
24     "Publicly-available inputs enable reproducibility and transparency",
25     "Quantified uncertainty per pixel via kriging SD (K)"
26   ],
27   "limitations": [
28     "Dependent on station density and interpolation quality (temperature ~500 stations, precipitation
29     ~2000 stations)",
30     "PHASE assumes temperature-driven phenology; extreme management/cultivar effects may be missed",
31     "Pixel-level positional errors (~22 km) affect local WI accuracy",
32     "Spatial and temporal basis risk persists in low-density or mountainous regions"
33   ],
34   "reproducibility_and_fairness": [
35     "Input data publicly available (DWD phenology/meteorology, REGNIE, SRTM DEM)",
36     "Workflow implemented in R with standard packages (raster, caret, PHASE, regression-kriging) for
37     reproducibility",
38     "Derived rasters and WI outputs intended for public dissemination via JKI/EMRA portal",
39     "Standard raster formats and metadata (K, spatial resolution, units) enable interoperability and
40     reuse"
41   ]
42 }
43 ]
```

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